

Iraq's Sovereign Wealth Fund Is An Economic Necessity For Sustainable Development

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Abstract

The Iraqi economy is suffering from many problems and crises caused by the wrong policies, unjustified wars and the economic blockade imposed by the Security Council of the United Nations(UNSC) using Article 41 of the Charter of the United Nations, by resolution 661 (661) of 6/4/1990, issued by the executive branch of the Organization of State, which called on all countries to refrain from any trade exchanges with Iraq, except for medical and food supplies, and this decision was the result of the invasion of Kuwaiti territory by Iraqi forces.

Introduction

As a result of the political and security instability after the American occupation of the Iraqi lands in April 2003, and the accompanying efforts in rebuilding the country, putting the ideology of the new political system and its new economic identity. The accompanying direct and rapid transition to a market economy and many problems associated with it which have affected the overall economic process.

The Iraqi economy is characterized by being a single-sided revenue - generating economy that depends on oil exports directly, and this characteristic makes it more vulnerable and affects external variables in terms of low oil prices or domestic in terms of low production, this will affect the overall situation in the country. There is an imbalance in public investment in terms of providing the right environment to attract foreign investment or the absence of the necessary infrastructure for investment, as this has been an impact and is accompanied by the deterioration of the service sector as a matter of course. Not to mention the deterioration of the agricultural sector and the absence and absence of the industrial sector. In addition, there are many challenges that hinder the development of the Iraqi economy, such as corruption, unemployment, poverty, inflation and external indebtedness.

Research problem

Despite the above-mentioned problems, the real problem is that the Iraqi economy is totally dependent on oil export revenues, the latter is a depleted resource and the possibility of finding alternatives to replace it by its consuming countries (such as shale oil).

Research hypothesis

The researcher assumes that sovereign wealth funds have a big role in protecting the national economy, especially those countries whose economy a single-sided revenue - generating economy. because these funds provide protection of the state's public budget, justice among generations and diversification of the economy through jobs that this has a positive impact on resource development and sustainability in development.

The importance of research

The research aims to develop and increase the state's resources by diversifying its economy and achieving sustainable development objectives through the functions and objectives sought by sovereign funds. Accordingly, the research is divided into several axes and is as follows:

Introduction

The first section: the concept of sovereign wealth funds

The Second section: The Importance of Sovereign Wealth Funds

The Third section: The establishment and financing of Iraq's sovereign wealth fund

The Fourth section: Iraq's Sovereign Wealth Fund and Sustainable Development

Conclusions and results.

The first section: the concept of sovereign wealth funds

First: Definition of sovereign wealth funds

Sovereign wealth funds vary into many types, including stability and savings funds, stabilization funds and generation funds, etc. the actual control of the government is different, the actual control of the government is also different, so a comprehensive definition is given to it, and the Deutsche Bank report summarizes the distinctive features of sovereign wealth funds as follows (sovereign funds are separately managed away from central bank reserves, dealing more with foreign currencies, lack of clear legal responsibilities, greater risk-bearing capacity. Long-term investment horizon, the possibility of strategic investments to enhance the country's returns.*

Sovereign funds are not a new phenomenon, but they date back to 1953, as it was the first sovereign fund in the world established by the State of Kuwait under the name of the Kuwait Investment Authority, which is now called the General Investment Authority and in 1969 there were only three funds in the world, This phenomenon expanded. Singapore established in 1974, the Temasek Sovereign Fund, which is financed through foreign trade, followed by the United Arab Emirates in 1976, with the establishment of the Abu Dhabi Investment Authority Fund, which is financed through oil surpluses and it is currently one of the world's largest sovereign funds.†

However, this phenomenon has been spreading and has become seen as investment funds that governments create or own in order to hold financial assets for long-term purposes, and these funds are usually financed by the state reserves themselves from foreign exchange reserves or state exports from Natural resources or the general revenues of the state.

As Iraq is one of the largest oil countries in the world with Stabilized and unstabilized reserves and is about to revolutionize production, export and hoped to be the equivalent of (Norwegian serum or vaccine) Counteracting the symptoms of (Dutch disease)‡, so we must build a sovereign fund and link it with the general budget by taking advantage of the opportunity to grace natural resources on the one hand and the availability of basic elements, whether political, economic, human or social.§ Taking the wisdom of wasting the opportunity is a waste of time or the security of the heartbreak.**

The International Monetary Fund defined SWFs as "public investment funds or arrangements with specific economic objectives (medium or long-term), owned and controlled by governments, built from foreign exchange operations, privatization returns, public fiscal surpluses or returns. Commodity exports, and these funds apply strategies that include investments in foreign financial assets, "this definition includes revenue stabilization funds, savings funds, development finance funds and government pension funds.††

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development of sovereign funds (OECD) is defined as a set of financial assets directly or indirectly managed by the government to achieve economic objectives financed either by foreign exchange reserves or by the state's exports of resources. natural or public revenue or any other resources."‡‡

The International Institute of Sovereign Wealth Funds (IIB) has defined them as government investment funds consisting of various financial assets such as stocks, bonds and other financial assets, financed by the surplus achieved in the private sector, the general budget, the balance of payments, or the surplus income from The export of goods is different from other state institutions, such as the central bank, which manages foreign reserves to achieve monetary policy objectives and differs from pension funds and economic companies.as "a financial means of the state arising from the liquidity achieved in the public sector or from the central bank's existing fiscal surplus."§§

This means that sovereign wealth funds are charged with managing the international reserves of state governments that have savings that consistently exceed any successive current account surpluses, owned by the state consisting of assets such as land, stocks, bonds, or other investment agencies, Assets excluded from sovereign wealth funds include foreign exchange reserves held by monetary authorities for traditional balance-of-payments and monetary policy purposes, Monetary policy, or the funds of state-owned enterprises in their traditional sense, or pension funds for government employees, can be described as financial entities or conglomerates that manage state surpluses for investment, resource development and social justice in society. Through these definitions, sovereign wealth funds share three characteristics:

1. It is fully state-owned and financed by the state's over-needed reserves, i.e. it does not need to be consumed or used to finance development projects. In this sense, sovereign funds can be said to be a means of

employing the accumulated external assets of the concerned state due to surpluses in the current account balance, or because of surpluses in the government budget.

2. They are not obliged to make periodic payments similar to those made to pension funds. The lack of commitment to periodic payments reinforces the tendency for these funds to favor long-term investment strategies. On the basis of this tendency, sovereign funds are fundamentally different from pension funds, which are committed to taking into account their debt and the resulting periodic monetary obligations.

3. These funds are managed free from foreign exchange reserves, i.e. they operate free from the policies implemented by the National Central Bank in the area of foreign reserves and the investment of these reserves.

Second: Types of sovereign wealth funds

Sovereign wealth funds can be divided on the basis of financed financial sources as they are divided into:

1. Sovereign funds based on natural wealth such as oil, natural gas and similar mineral wealth.

2. Sovereign funds based on foreign exchange reserves transferred by the Central Bank in cases of fiscal surpluses.

There are those who divide them on the basis of the objective or objectives they seek to achieve, and accordingly they are divided into:

1- Stability funds: This type of funds are suitable for the economy of the countries rich in natural resources, in order to isolate the general budget and the macroeconomic with fluctuations in the prices of these materials, they seek to achieve stability in the overall situation in the country, in anticipation of changing circumstances and internal variables, such as low production of natural resources or oil or external variables such as low demand or low prices.

These funds seek to protect the general budget of the state and the economy as a whole and stabilize the exchange rate of their currencies against balance-of-payments fluctuations, which arise mainly from fluctuations in commodity prices, particularly oil.^{***} These funds are a means of filling the government budget need in the event that natural resource prices fall to certain levels.

2- Savings funds: Unlike its predecessor, if stability funds are pursuing near and medium goals, savings funds seek to achieve long-term goals or meet the conditions of sustainable development, and to alleviate the so-called Dutch disease.

These funds seek to convert non-renewable resources or financial assets into more stable resources by investing them in various investments, as they aim to provide the necessary financial resources in the future through the returns of these investments, helping to maintain the level of national income or working to increase it.^{†††}

3- Processes related to the investment of reserves: are financial assets that are normally established or held by the Central Bank, whose main objective is to obtain financial return regardless of the potential risks.^{†††}

4-Development funds: These funds are very important for developing and oil-producing countries^{§§§}, as the state is using its resources towards projects with economic and social priority, specifically infrastructure projects, i.e. they help finance projects with an economic and social objective.^{****}

5-Pension Reserve Funds: These are funds that are employed in order to sustain the salaries and pensions of the pension stipend, and these funds are sometimes used as a pattern to meet the occasional obligations that occur urgently on the state balance sheet.^{††††} It should be noted that this mechanism is contrary to the contributions made by individuals to pensions.^{****}

Therefore, sovereign funds are distinct from central banks from their objectives, they seek investment, not monetary and exchange policy management, and they invest bonds, although some countries such as China and Norway entrust the management of their sovereign funds to central banks in favor of the Ministry of Finance.

It is distinguished from public pension funds that the latter's resources come mainly from contributions and are intended to finance them, but sovereign funds aim to invest the country's surplus savings for investment purposes.^{§§§§}

In summary, there is a trend towards the establishment of sovereign funds, especially for the countries exporting mineral resources, through which they seek to achieve a set of objectives determined by the type of funds, there are funds that provide funds for older persons, especially in the old societies, while others aim to use their funds in development programs, investments and diversification of national economic income

mechanisms, while funds are designed to mitigate sudden price increases, currency volatility and general international economic instability.*****

The Second Section: The Importance of Sovereign Wealth Funds

Some economists believe that sovereign funds have become the focus of wide spread of interest among many governments, especially after the worsening of crises and economic problems, in addition to the low oil prices in the world markets, which have negatively affected the producing and exporting countries, which have collected Billions of dollars of the profits of selling oil in previous years, which may contribute to reducing its financial and economic damage, in addition to being an important investment tool and a means of expanding the economic base and diversifying sources of income.†††††

Sovereign wealth funds are one of the most important institutional instruments that manage the financial surpluses of states to invest in order to achieve a range of common objectives of protecting and stabilizing the budget and economy from excessive fluctuations in revenues and exports and diversifying their exports of non-renewable commodities and generating greater returns from focusing on foreign exchange reserves, helping monetary authorities to spend unwanted liquidity and playing the reserve role of their own countries by transferring part of their returns to future generations Financing the development of sustainable development in all its dimensions and contributing to the development of the host countries through the financing of base structures.†††††

The importance of sovereign funds is also due to their use in infrastructure projects, in addition to social service investments from hospitals, schools and real estate, and sovereign funds are considered investment funds, a number of which aim to protect the budget and economy from fluctuations in commodity prices. Basic, the savings funds represent for future generations and aim to convert assets into reserves and contribute to increased return and development.

The main reasons for increasing the importance of sovereign funds can be summed up in three reasons:

First- High oil prices: High oil prices for the producing countries lead to large financial savings that may be beyond their need, which requires them to invest in medium and long-term projects, by establishing sovereign funds that maintain this financial abundance independent of the country's financial policy and use them for the purpose of investing them internally or externally to maximize benefit and increase development, or use them for the purpose of protecting their macroeconomics.

Second: The emergence of economic-financial globalization. The economic globalization defines as the integration of the economies of nations, without any geographical, political or economic barriers such as tariffs on goods and services.

One of the positive effects of economic globalization since its emergence is the acceleration of development in the telecommunications sector, which was accompanied by the spread of the Internet, which provided modern means that contributed to the service of the economic sector and success in business, and economic globalization depended on economic integration, i.e. association a country's domestic economy with the world economy, which improves the economy of countries, and the appropriate use of available resources, that provides financial adequacy for every country in the world.

Globalization, specifically financial liberalization and the transition to financial integration, leads to the integration and association of domestic financial markets with foreign markets through the elimination of the movement and flow of capital to countries, which facilitates their transition to financial markets. for the state. Increased capital flows have been helped by cash instruments that were not known in the financial and monetary system (e.g. derivatives, receivers and currency options), reflecting the importance of establishing and the role of sovereign funds.

Third: Imbalances in the global financial system: Sovereign wealth funds are becoming increasingly important in the international monetary and financial system, as a result of their impact on financial stability and capital flows throughout the world, i.e. to avoid falling into financial crises that represent a sharp and sudden upheaval, sovereign wealth funds have played a major role in reducing the effects of recent financial crises and setbacks in global financial markets.

Therefore, it can be said that resorting to sovereign funds is of great importance to many countries, especially developing ones, for their ability to cope with economic instability, and this importance has been reinforced by the repeated financial crises, particularly the crisis of 2008, which resulted that there are emerging economies that have been able to Getting out of the financial crisis is relatively safe due to its financial savings and sovereign funds. Since then, the importance of sovereign funds has increased, and this importance is highlighted in addition to the following:

- 1) Depletion of the natural resource oil and here we must look for other resources that provide income to replace the income of the natural resource that can be depleted and the use of its revenues for all generations, i.e. protecting the national economy and the general budget of the state from the risk of external crises that come from fluctuations resulting from export revenues.
- 2) Achieving the principle of justice among generations.
- 3) The diversification of the state's income and the expansion of the economic base, thereby reducing dependence on non-renewable commodity exports such as Iraq and the Gulf countries that depend on oil.
- 4) The mechanism of increasing the returns of reserves for foreign exchange.
- 5) The Monetary Authority helps to withdraw unwanted liquidity
- 6) Providing a tool to finance economic development programs
- 7) Achieving long-term sustainable growth for fund-owning countries
- 8) Achieving political objectives such as the security and stability of the political and economic system such as maintaining the budget, protecting the national economy and the general budget from collapse, diversifying the country's incomes, working to reduce dependence on rent-seeking exports and achieve long-term sustainable growth.
- 9) The presence of negative effects as a result of the flows resulting from natural wealth or what is known as the Dutch disease if these people become lazy and lax as a result of their dependence on oil and gas, as they went to luxury and comfort until they reached the stage of depletion of natural resources.
- 10) 10-It may be used to finance deficits in pension funds or social security contributions due to ageing compared to the labor force, thus becoming an imbalance between pensions and the value of contributions provided by the labor force, and their role is to cover future financing requirements.
- 11) But it does not mean that there is no fearful and opposed trend for the emergence and spread of sovereign funds, a report published by geo economica^{sssss} group, for political risk research showed that the majority among the largest sovereign wealth funds in the world lack transparency and appropriate governance and that the levels of transparency of the Gulf of which they were very low. Geo Economica valued the performance of a sovereign wealth fund with a total asset of \$4 trillion to determine its commitment to the Santiago Principles.
- 12) Geo Economics stated in its index of compliance with the Santiago Principles, which it publishes annually three years ago "Many funds, particularly from the Gulf region, should make significant improvements to financial disclosure policies and be more transparent about governance arrangements, and the study found that nine funds were considered to be fully compliant," Geo Economics said in its index of compliance with the Santiago Principles. while nine others were generally compliant, but eight others fulfilled only part of their obligations and lacked strong financial information such as audited statements, balance sheets or standard performance indicators.

The Santiago Principles were prepared in 2008 amid concerns about the growing influence of funds in financial markets and concerns that some of them would make investments for political rather than purely commercial purposes, as well as the fact that the Davos Economic Conference in Switzerland confirmed that its objectives might be political, making it a topic of widespread interest in The financial and monetary system, the conference witnessed a great debate about the nature, pattern and intentions of physical investments.

Third section: The establishment and financing of Iraq's sovereign wealth fund

First, establishment of the Fund

With the increase in fiscal surpluses of oil-producing and exporting countries, the lack of the right investment climate to absorb those surpluses, as well as the weak capacity of national economies to absorb the fiscal surpluses achieved, and to reduce the risk element, many of these governments of Countries have gone to invest these surpluses in financial institutions and companies in more stable and secure countries, especially developed countries economically because of the political and economic climates that are conducive to attracting investments, especially as capital seeks a secure and stable environment.*****

As far as Iraq is concerned, the Iraq Development Fund, which was established by the Interim Coalition Authority and recognized by UN Security Council Resolution 1483, has already been established, but because of the nature of its composition, the circumstances in which the country has gone through it and the nature of the occupation in general, it led to the waste of Iraqi funds, which can be described as a fund to meet the obligations, all his resources did not go to rebuild the country, but went to finance the expenses of the war machine,⁺⁺⁺⁺⁺ as this fund differs from the sovereign wealth funds as it does not have a clear strategy to depend on it in the management of financial resources, but in our time The present can form a sovereign fund, but it must be met with the highest requirements of transparency and accountability.

In addition, are the fundamentals of establishing this fund available?*****

- 1) If we look at the political fundamentals: we find that there is a representative council elected by the general public in a free and democratic way, whose choice is supposed to be based on efficiency, integrity, honesty and the will to change for the better and work on it, and this is available to keep the legislation of a law by the House of Representatives to be built on that the necessity of establishing this fund and providing it with the legal framework necessary for its creation and the exercise of its work.
- 2) Economic fundamentals: embodied in the presence and abundance of mineral natural resources, including oil, gas and non-mineral, the presence of manpower, capital and human capital.
- 3) Qualified human capital: Qualified human resources mean the human being who is the means of development and its purpose is able to absorb and excel in advanced information and his ability to build funds on solid foundations and manage them efficiently. The Central Bank of Iraq is also able to provide or train administrative staff who are experienced in economic matters in general, management and investment in particular.
- 4) The most important of all is the availability of political will, which believes in the need to change the existing situation, along with the availability of honesty, integrity, love of the homeland and responsibility, through which it is possible to ensure the integrity of the management and use of public funds efficiently.

Second, fund funding

Sovereign wealth funds are generally funded in one of two ways:

The first method is to separate or isolate the surplus in the general budget if it exists and this surplus is deposited in the fund and during any period of the fiscal year provided that a supplementary budget is not made to spend this surplus because Iraq has resorted to this issue since 2009 to supplementary budgets because of its access to additional resources as a result of the rise in oil prices, 70% of the consumption and operating spending was spent, which is not useful, and this led to the absorption of the principles of fiscal policy and its economic and social effects and its reflection on economic indicators, especially the collapse of the productive sectors of the state economy. . Like Norway.

Or it would be in a second way: a certain percentage of oil revenues should be deducted directly throughout the fiscal year in a sovereign fund, as in the Kuwaiti Generation fund, which has set 10 percent of total oil revenues.

In Iraq, we propose to use the two methods in addition to transferring part of the reserves of the Central Bank of Iraq, or to calculate the difference between the increase in the price of one barrel of oil and what is fixed and based on the state budget, i.e. in the case of an increase in oil prices, the state does not resort to a supplementary budget. This money is saved in the sovereign fund in order to invest it.

Third: The purpose and objective of establishing sovereign wealth funds in Iraq

After the country emerged victorious from terrorism in general against the terrorist gangs (ISIS) in particular, the need to generate revenue to finance reconstruction efforts, as well as the need that the country whose economy depends on oil can diversify this economy, as oil prices allow the Iraqi government The opportunity to finance reconstruction efforts and improve the country's infrastructure, but the country's dependence on unstable commodities due to volatile oil prices that could lead to a direct collapse of the economy. So there must be a true and strong relationship on which to face these risks, and to ensure that revenues from oil wealth are used in the direction of reconstruction, allowing the Iraqi economy to become more sustainable and resilient against price shocks. §§§§§§

Therefore, this fund must be established in order to achieve a set of objectives, which reflect positively on the entire Iraqi economy and these objectives are:*****

- 1- To counter the negative shocks caused by the instability of oil prices in the world oil markets, which have had effects on many economic, social and political factors in Iraq
 - 2- To face the decline in oil demand due to the replacement of more efficient resources (shale oil) from the oil consuming countries themselves.
 - 3- Anticipation of the natural depletion of the resource and the need for a resource or other resources to generate income to compensate for the depletion of oil.
 - 4- The capacity of the Iraqi economy and the potential of diversification, which depends on the volume of production and oil reserves.
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- 5- Negative repercussions of the financial flows resulting from oil or what is known as the Dutch disease and the need to maintain the stability of economic activity from the repercussions of this disease on the Iraqi economy.
- 6- To keep up with the overall policies of the oil countries and the mechanisms used to create sovereign wealth funds
- 7- Sovereign funds contribute to the transfer of technology to the countries that own these funds through direct and indirect investments with developed countries.

As far as this is concerned in Iraq, the establishment of this fund becomes an absolute necessity for sustainable development, because of its advantages, such as:

- 1- Contributing to macroeconomic stability through general stability through the stability and regularity of revenues flowing into the general budget (especially Iraq depends on oil and any defect that occurs affecting the budget deficit)
- 2-The Fund becomes an important tool for financing economic and social development programs.
- 3- Maximizing the directing saving for future generations of oil-exporting supplier and achieving the principle of justice in achieving justice among generations.
- 4- Curbing the expansion of government spending, especially consumer and operating spending.
- 5-The Fund's resources are an important source of budget deficits with certain limits.

The fourth section: The Sovereign Fund in Iraq and the Achievement of Sustainable Development.

Sustainable development is the preparation of resource development plans that do not aim to drain natural resources and affect their type, but rather improve people's standard of living and well-being by developing resources for current generations and future generations, and the greatest burden is on the state and its institutions as well as society and individuals. *****

The follow-up to the Iraqi economic affairs in the last decade, especially after the removal of all structures and sectors already dilapidated as a result of the American occupation and looting, as it notes the increasing dependence of Iraq on oil imports in the management of the development process and the development of the country's infrastructure, and what accompanied this dependence of a decline in the role of other production sectors such as industrial, agricultural, manufacturing and other sectors, where this increased dependence led to many economic and social problems, including the decline of the monetary revenues required to carry out the development process and promote With service projects in the hands of oil in the absence of other sources of income and the decline in their economic performance.

Thus, it itself became dependent on oil revenues for its durability and survival, and here a larger and more complex problem emerged, namely the correlation of the development process with world oil prices, which are inherently unstable and subject to several factors that are difficult to predict and calculate, if their prices decrease. For one reason or another it has negatively impacted on service projects and infrastructure of exporting countries that are no longer preparing for this day, as happened in the wake of the decline and collapse of oil prices globally in 2014 and their decline after reaching the limits of \$120 per barrel prices fell to reach about 30 dollars for the same barrel, The resulting austerity in most oil countries, including Iraq, has halted most construction and reconstruction projects in the country, even at high levels of achievement. *****

So what sovereign wealth funds do is important for the development of the country, they usually help finance economic projects that can promote the growth of potential output in the economy in question, they have a role to play on the economy of their owners and receiving countries, where they can exert a balanced influence for sovereign wealth funds in a variety of ways, at the national level, the latter gave government authorities the ability to manage capital inputs while solving persistent structural problems, enabling them to support the economic growth of some countries.

At the international level, sovereign wealth funds are able to provide liquidity and investment to help global markets in times of economic crisis, because of their high savings and strategies for medium- and long-term investment. It is a tool for achieving sustainable development as there are many common objectives linking the concepts of sovereign funds and sustainable development, first and foremost the preservation of sources of wealth and the attempt to develop them through their investment and the latter is one of the most important activities in order to achieve economic development and long-term sustainable development. As other instruments for generating income and GDP, as well as the possibility of investing them in stabilizing and financing the country's budget deficit, these funds provide a financial abundance for the country that will keep it safe from changes in oil prices.

It can therefore be said that sovereign funds contribute to the creation of development and sustainable development, through the means they do and these means are:

First- Eliminating the curse of resources and reducing the effects of the Dutch disease: one of the symptoms of this disease is to increase the financial revenues of the state as a result of the export of oil resources, but this abundance is accompanied by a lack of employment opportunities, and this applies to Iraq, as the increase in the export of oil, which in turn leads to the appreciation of the local currency, this makes national industry less competitive with goods than other countries. This industry is one of those industries that does not accommodate large numbers of unemployed people, and requires huge capital intensity and a high level of skills.

According to this theory, the economies of countries rich in extractive goods are developing slower than those with little or no natural resources, and may sometimes face negative growth, or their populations may become lazy by relying on natural resources without developing industrial sectors. The other one. This results in a reversal between the abundance of resources and the lack of economic growth, and governments may resort to high welfare systems, or eliminate taxes to maintain public stability, while others follow the method of imposing the blockade, yet these structures lead to the erosion of the social contract between the rulers and the governed. It prevents the ruling class from being motivated to seek the welfare of the people, while encouraging members of the ruling class to engage in corrupt activities. §§§§§§

The success or failure of the development process does not depend on the availability of natural resources and assistance, but rather requires the creation of a political, economic and cultural environment that pits growth, encourages innovations, the rule of law and the protection of intellectual property, which will contribute to the introduction of various options and viable plans. It strengthens the process of building the right foundations for the establishment of the sovereign fund in line with the current environment.

To prevent these risks, foreign exchange savings must be used to ease the pressure of the national currency increase and protect the general budget. Sovereign funds can help diversify the economy by investing in various economic sectors within the single economy, which will create sectorial integration between different economic sectors through internal and external savings. So that each sector becomes complementary to the other sector, which helps in increasing exports and reducing imports

Because sovereign wealth funds are a barrier between the income-generating sector and the broader economy, and they are a barrier between the latter and the global economy by preventing direct and immediate impacts of currency shocks, lower returns and reducing the effects of global economic crises. It is also capable of mitigating the effects of the resource curse and Dutch disease, as it focuses on strengthening the country's net foreign assets structure in a manner consistent with and preserving economic and social structures.

Second - Investment: The investment function is one of the most important jobs that sovereign funds perform and it means investing or using the funds of the sovereign fund in the field of investment, whether direct or indirect, it is a basic requirement and necessary to promote sustainable development, especially as one of the most important goals of investment is to increase wealth And working to develop them, and to achieve this, sovereign wealth funds invested their money to invest in various economic sectors, especially in developed countries, which are characterized by encouraging conditions such as political and economic stability enjoyed by these countries, and the development of their financial and economic markets.

Despite the importance of investment, but as far as the matter is concerned with Iraq, some believe that the Iraqi governments lack the experience and economic experience to participate in such investments without incurring unnecessary losses, and also recommend these funds when the government has ample savings that exceed its need and projects, and this matter is lacking Mechanism of the Iraqi economy at the moment

Third- Financing and financial stability: Financing plays an important role in the economies of countries, whether in the form of loans, grants or foreign investment, it is possible that sovereign funds can provide them unconditionally, or sovereign funds serve as stores used by countries in times of insolvency represented by the decline in the state's financial revenue, because of low oil prices, funds here are protecting the balance sheet and not resorting to external borrowing, and they are working to achieve financial stability through investment decisions made by sovereign funds or because of the hedging strategy taken by sovereign funds in some. Sometimes in order to maintain the balance of the investment portfolio against potential losses.

Conclusion and recommendations

The Iraqi economy is a rentier economy that depends mainly on oil and gas revenues in the composition of the country's general budget, and there are no other tributaries to raise the state budget, and if there is a very small contribution. This budget is spent with consumer and operational spending without focusing on investment spending, which means that the country is not moving towards development and sustainable development, and perhaps even plans to boost the economy and rebuild infrastructures while this situation continues to succeed, in addition to this an important issue is A change in the volume of oil revenues toward scaling means that the state stops all of its projects and takes austerity measures.

Therefore, a stabilization fund must be built to support the public budget, as well as sovereign wealth funds perform a key task in diversifying the Iraqi economy by supporting development projects, building other

projects, supporting the agriculture sector and boosting the industrial sector, thus contributing to the integration of the sectors. The different economies of the country, as it is not harmful to benefit from the experiences of other countries such as Norway, and thus can contribute to comprehensive and sustainable development.

1- Recommendations

- 2- Measures must be taken to establish a stability fund in order to achieve the goals mentioned, and this fund is financed from the difference between the price of a barrel that is based on the state's general budget and the price of sale in global markets in the event of a difference in the direction of the rise. Or it is determined that 3% of the oil revenues are deposited in this fund. It is not among the reserves held by the Central Bank.
- 3- That the sovereign funds are subject to the management of a higher council for economic policies, and this is an independent council that includes competencies and expertise. There is no harm in benefiting from the experiences from outside the country.
- 4- The presence of an independent body with powers for permanent control of all matters relating to sovereign funds, and this body shall submit its reports to the competent authorities, for the sake of accountability.
- 5- The transparency and accountability formulas must be adopted in managing this fund.
- 6- Close coordination between the state's macroeconomic objectives and the sovereign fund's plans.
- 7- Evaluating the fund's work with the announced plans and goals that must be measurable, with conformity with the actual reality.
- 8- Benefiting from the experiences of other countries in establishing and financing sovereign funds, such as Norway, and making these funds as a vaccine or a cure for Dutch disease that has afflicted Iraqi society and fights resource curse.
- 9- Sovereign fund investments should be directed towards economic and social development among the internal sectors of the State, and after internal development, it is possible to go abroad in a deliberate manner.

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